

P-56

64 -
51 -
39 -
28 -

64 -
51 -
39 -
28 -

10 wells

3.15.18

Phospho
GapdH

phospho
GapdH

Total
GapdH

Total
GapdH

AKK →
1249

← Total
AKK

AKK
Total →

Total
AKK